

Law of Conservation of Energy of Gravitational Fields and the Gravitational Field Equation

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Abstract

A gravitational field equation has been found that is completely in keeping with all of the postulates of Einstein's Theory of Relativity and the Law of Conservation of Momentum and Energy. This is achieved by introducing the gravitational field into the energy-momentum tensor equation. In the region of the small fields possessed by smaller fields, the equation differs slightly from the Einstein equation and it is important to note that the solutions of the new equation do not contain singularities. The local law of conservation of energy-momentum of a system substance-gravitational field follows directly from the new equation. A numerical solution of the equation for a point source of the gravitational field was obtained.

Keywords: Energy-momentum conservation law, Gravitational field equation, Ricci tensor, Black holes, Rigorous solutions.

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1. Introduction

At the end of 1915 Einstein found the correct value of the rotation of the perihelion of Mercury [1] using this equation:

$$\frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x_{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta} = 0, \quad (1)$$

where the Christoffel symbols are defined as ².

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha} = \frac{1}{2} g^{\alpha\beta} \left(\frac{\partial g_{\beta\nu}}{\partial x^{\mu}} + \frac{\partial g_{\beta\mu}}{\partial x^{\nu}} - \frac{\partial g_{\mu\nu}}{\partial x^{\beta}} \right),$$

This result showed that the taking into account of the (small) energy density of the gravitational field has little or no significant effect.

Finally, Einstein's equation (December 1915 [2])³,

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \kappa \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} T \right), \quad (2)$$

where is the Ricci tensor is described as followers:

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\nu}} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\beta} \quad (3)$$

In the same article, Einstein published the modern Einstein equation, in a now forgotten, "simplified" form:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x_{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta} = \kappa \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} T \right). \\ \sqrt{-g} = 1. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

² In his work, Einstein defines symbols with the opposite sign.

³ The introduction of the trace $T = T_{\mu}^{\mu}$ into the equation leads to the automatic fulfillment of the law of conservation of energy and momentum of matter and the electromagnetic fields.

In the simplified form the equation was solved by Schwarzschild [3]. Due to the complexity of this solution, this kind of equation has disappeared from the literature.

The above equation however, was not the equation originally conceived two years ago [4]. According to Einstein, the equation of gravitational fields must satisfy and comply with the requirement that is mandatory and called for under the Relativistic Theory of Gravity. It should show that the momentum energy tensors of the gravitational field and the matter present are equally sources of the gravitational field. At the same time, Einstein made an important remark when he stated: "The exceptional position of the energy of the gravitational field in comparison with all other types of energy would lead to unacceptable consequences" [4].

The law of conservation of matter and the gravitational field does not follow from Einstein's equation, but was provided for by the introduction of the gravitational field pseudotensor, the elements of which were associated with the energy-momentum densities and stresses of the gravitational field. However, the proof of the law of conservation of energy-momentum exists only in and for closed systems and it contains quantities that are supposedly components of the gravitational field itself. Thus the absence of a full-fledged conservation law, which follows from the field equation, results in the theory of gravity being incomplete.

Despite the huge success of the General Theory of Relativity, the question of the applicability of equation (3) with regard to strong fields, when the energy of the gravitational field cannot be neglected, has thus been left open.

The energy-momentum tensor of the gravitational field $f_{\mu\nu}$ found earlier [5] and the new equation, the refined equation of the gravitational field of the gravitational field [6]. Here it is shown that the energy-momentum tensor $f_{\mu\nu}$ has the correct energy density in the Newtonian field limit. This confirms the initial calibration of the $f_{\mu\nu}$ tensor value.

2. Einstein's Division of the Ricci Tensor

Einstein explored the possibility of simplifying the gravitational field equation [7] and [8]. In order to do so the Ricci tensor

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\nu}} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\beta}$$

was represented as the sum of two covariant tensors

$$R_{\mu\nu} = A_{\mu\nu} + B_{\mu\nu};$$

$$A_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta};$$

$$B_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\nu}} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\beta} \quad \therefore$$

$$B_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{\partial \ln \sqrt{-g}}{\partial x^{\mu} \partial x^{\nu}} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha} \frac{\partial \ln \sqrt{-g}}{\partial x^{\alpha}}.$$

Einstein showed that choosing coordinates such that $\sqrt{-g} = 1$ nullifies $B_{\mu\nu}$. Thus this leads to a simplified form of the equation (4). However, according to that equation we do not yet know whether parts of the Ricci tensor are in fact actual tensor quantities.

So let us prove that they are:

Theorem 1. *The quantity $\Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}$ is a 4-vector, and $B_{\mu\nu}$ is a tensor.*

This is P r o o f. We used the formula for the coordinate transformation of Christoffel symbols (equation (85.15), [7])

$$\Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\iota} = \Gamma_{\nu\xi}^{\iota\gamma} \frac{\partial x^{\iota}}{\partial x^{\nu}} \frac{\partial x^{\gamma}}{\partial x^{\xi}} + \frac{\partial^2 x^{\iota\gamma}}{\partial x^{\alpha} \partial x^{\nu}} \frac{\partial x^{\nu}}{\partial x^{\xi}}$$

If we are to add the following to this expression, $\iota = \alpha$ and $\gamma = \xi$, then the formula will be simplified as seen below:

$$\Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha} = \Gamma_{\nu\xi}^{\alpha\xi} \frac{\partial x^{\nu}}{\partial x^{\mu}}.$$

Thus, $\Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}$ transforms into a 4-vector and hence is in fact a 4-vector.

The covariant differentiation $\Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}$ generates the tensor

$$D \Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha} = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\nu}} - \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\beta},$$

the resulting tensor possesses and exactness up to the sign and is $B_{\mu\nu}$.

It follows from the proven theorem that since $R_{\mu\nu}$ is a tensor, it follows from $R_{\mu\nu} = A_{\mu\nu} + B_{\mu\nu}$ that $A_{\mu\nu}$ is also in fact a tensor quantity.

3. The Connection of Part of Tensor $B_{\mu\nu}$ with the Gravitational Field

The fact that the value of $B_{\mu\nu}$ can be reset to zero by choosing the coordinates of the inertial frame may mean that it is associated with the gravitational field. This is proven by the fact that a gravitational field can also be nullified at a given point by the transition to the accompanying inertial frame of reference [9] (equivalence principle).

Consider the quantity $B_{\mu\nu}$ in the Newtonian approximation, which is described by the stationary metric:

$$ds^2 = \left(1 + \frac{2\varphi}{c^2}\right) dt^2 - g_{xx} dx^2 - g_{yy} dy^2 - g_{zz} dz^2,$$

here $\varphi(x)$ is the Newtonian potential. Taking into account that the spatial components of the metric tensor and its determinant slightly differ from unity, we thus obtain

$$B_{00} = \Gamma_{00}^1 \Gamma_{1\beta}^{\beta} = \frac{1}{g_{xx} c^2} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{1}{c^2 + \varphi} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \approx -\frac{1}{c^4} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x}\right)^2. \quad (5)$$

The energy density of the gravitational field in the Newtonian approximation is known ([9] § 106, problem 1):

$$f_{00} = -\frac{(\nabla\varphi)^2}{8\pi G}$$

from where we get the following:

$$B_{00} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} f_{00} = \kappa f_{00}.$$

This relation allows us to connect the tensor $B_{\mu\nu}$ with the energy-momentum-stress tensor of the gravitational field $f_{\mu\nu}$

$$B_{\mu\nu} = \kappa f_{\mu\nu}. \quad (6)$$

5. Gravitational Field Equation

Einstein's equation (4) does not contain the energy tensor of the gravitational field because the condition $\sqrt{-g} = 1$ “turns off” the energy of the gravitational field in this regard (5). Turning on the energy of the gravitational field is easy - you just need to abandon the associated and ridiculous condition in the Einstein equation. Then the gravitational field equation will appear as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x_{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta} = \kappa \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} T \right). \quad (7)$$

taking equation (6) into account leads to an equivalent equation with the energy-momentum tensor of the gravitational field

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \kappa \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} T + f_{\mu\nu} \right). \quad (7')$$

or the field equation with the Einstein tensor:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \kappa (T_{\mu\nu} + f_{\mu\nu}). \quad (7'')$$

For a space in which there is nothing but the gravitational field, the gravitational field equation (7) takes the form:

$$\frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x_{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta} = 0. \quad (8)$$

Theorem 2. Equation (7'') follows the implications of the law of conservation of energy-momentum of the system of matter and the gravitational field.

P r o o f. Since the covariant divergence of the Einstein tensor $G_{\nu;\mu}^{\mu} \equiv 0$ equation (7'') we are led to the following identity:

$$T_{\nu;\mu}^{\mu} + f_{\nu;\mu}^{\mu} \equiv 0,$$

which is an expression in complete compliance with the law of conservation of energy-momentum of matter and the gravitational field⁴.

Theorem 3. Within the limits of a weak gravitational field, Einstein's equation (4) is asymptotically equal to equation (7).

Proof. We introduce the tensor $h_{\mu\nu}$, which describes a weak perturbation of the Galilean metric:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu}^0 + h_{\mu\nu},$$

and the determinant of the tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$

$$g = -1 + h.$$

and $h = h^{\nu}_{\nu}$.

Then if $h \rightarrow 0$, then $\sqrt{-g} = 1$, whence it follows that Einstein's equation (4), within this limit is as close as desired and approaches equation (7). As can be seen in [1], Einstein, when solving problems involving the motion of Mercury and the deflection of light rays in the gravitational field of the Sun, used only the first equation of the system of equations (4), i.e. he actually used equation (7). Thus, the approximate solutions involving problems of the motion of Mercury and the deflection of light rays in the gravitational field of the Sun coincided with similar solutions reached by using said equation (7).

6. Solutions of the Gravitational Field Equation

⁴ From Einstein's equation follows only the matter aspect of the law of conservation of energy: $T_{\nu;\mu}^{\mu} \equiv 0$.

The most suitable problem for making a comparison is the problem of finding the gravitational field of a point mass (the Schwarzschild problem). Looking for solutions in the form

$$ds^2 = s(r)dt^2 - p(r)dr^2 - r^2d\theta^2 - r^2\sin^2\theta d\phi^2.$$

From equation (8), we find the components of the mixed tensor, up to a nonzero factor, which are equal to:

$$A_0^0 = \frac{s''}{s'} - \frac{p'}{p} - \frac{s'}{s},$$

$$A_1^1 = \left(\frac{p'}{p}\right)' - \frac{2}{r^2} - \frac{s's'}{4s^2},$$

where the prime signifies the derivative with respect to r . If we then equate these components to zero, we get a system of ordinary differential equations. Eliminating the value $\frac{p'}{p}$ from which we then obtain the equation

$$\left(\frac{s''}{s'}\right)' - \left(\frac{s'}{s}\right)' - \frac{s's'}{2s^2} = \frac{4}{r^2}. \quad (9)$$

If we take $s = e^v$, we can noticeably expand the range of stability of numerical methods for anomalously small values of s . In the vicinity of the Schwarzschild radius $r_g = 1$ (see figure), there are no singularities or deviations from the monotonic dependence of the solution.

In the area accessible to the applied numerical solution methods, there are no signs of an “event horizon”, singularities or a space other than the Riemann space with its given signature. The only anomaly near the origin is a flat area with a small potential close to the limiting potential $-c^2$.

Figure 1. Dependence of g_{00} ratio $\frac{r}{r_g}$. The Schwarzschild solution of the Einstein equation (dotted line) and the numerical solution of the exact equation of the gravitational field (8) (solid line).

Source: Author.

7. Discussion

We can now realistically take into consideration Einstein’s idea [4] regarding the inclusion of the energy tensor of the gravitational field in the correct equation of the gravitational field. It is thus shown that the new equation remains covariant and asymptotically, and for weak fields, its solutions are close to the solutions of the Einstein equation.

The numerical solution demonstrates real and positive values of g_{00} in the region smaller than the Schwarzschild radius (the region in which the solution of the Einstein equation for a point source of the field does not exist, known as the “black hole”, which then gave rise to a huge number of hypotheses, all of varying degrees of likelihood).

The Figure (1) shows the dependence of the solution of equation (9) $g_{00} = s(r)$ on the distance to the origin in comparison with the Schwarzschild solution $g_{00} = 1 - \frac{1}{r}$. First of all, we see that the numerical solution, in contrast to the Schwarzschild solution, has metric values belonging to the original pseudo-Riemannian space at $r > 0$, and quickly approaches the Schwarzschild solution as the field strength decreases. Moreover, $s(r)$ is a smooth non-negative function on the interval $r > 0$, this changes our understanding of the magnitude and nature of the gravitational field of heavy, compact

space objects. At the point r_g , we see the extremely small value of $g_{00} = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-273}$ and a remaining small positive value in the vicinity of

$$0 < r < 3.4 r_g.$$

This fantastically small value appears due to the fact that the source of gravity is a point. From the point of view of the General Theory of Relativity, this means that time in such a region has almost stopped and has a potential close to the limit $-c^2$. The solution of the equation will satisfy the requirement of V.A. Fock [10] - the absence of regions in which the speed of light is zero⁵.

The radius of the region possessing an extremely small potential is close in overall magnitude to the known determination used with regard to the radius of neutron stars. This suggests that the value of $3.4r_g$ determines the "firmament" of neutron stars. On a qualitative level the dependence $g_{00}(r)$ does not differ from the similar dependence of the Schwarzschild solution in a physically significant region. However, the interpretation of collisions of massive compact stellar objects observed with the LIGO & Virgo gravitational wave antennas will overestimate the mass of these objects. Perhaps a detailed study of the collisions of compact objects will show the features of the gravitational field of these objects [11].

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⁵ The Schwarzschild solution not only has a singular point r_g , but also a region not belonging to the original pseudo-Riemannian space $0 < r < r_g$.